

Integrated potential of vermicompost, elemental sulphur and *Glomus fasciculatum* induced phytoremediation of cadmium and lead contaminated alluvial soil by *Chrysanthemum indicum* L.

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Abstract : The integrated potential of vermicompost, elemental sulphur (S) and *Glomus fasciculatum* by growing *Chrysanthemum indicum* L. for phytoremediation of cadmium and lead contaminated soils was investigated under pot experiment. The integrated treatment T₆ (6 g kg⁻¹ vermicompost, 0.8 g kg⁻¹ S and inoculation with *G. fasciculatum*) promoted the dry biomass of the plant. The treatment was feasible for enhanced cadmium accumulation up to 6.69 and 5.66 mg kg⁻¹ and lead accumulation up to 16.70 and 13.74 mg kg⁻¹ in root and shoot, respectively, which caused maximum remediation efficiency (0.55% and 0.18%) and bioaccumulation factor (2.57 and 0.84) for Cd and Pb, respectively at the Naini contaminated site (S₂). Thus, authors conclude to integrate vermicompost, elemental sulphur and inoculation with *Glomus fasciculatum* for enhanced clean-up of cadmium and lead-contaminated soils.

Keywords : *Chrysanthemum indicum* L., heavy metals, phytoremediation, vermicompost, *Glomus fasciculatum*, elemental sulphur.

Introduction

Metals are the most prevalent forms in the environment, and their remediation in soils is a difficult task. Soil pollution by heavy metals is a global environmental problem as it has affected about 235 million hectares of arable land worldwide¹. Contaminated soils may be remediated by physical, chemical or biological techniques but the physical or chemical methods can be very costly and also destructive to the soil ecosystem. Phytoextraction or hyperaccumulation, one of the biological techniques, has been proposed as an eco-friendly *in situ* remediation technology for the contaminated soils². However, the technique has several advantages and disadvantages as well^{3,4}. Low biomass production in hyperaccumulator plants and susceptibility of root to high metal concentration lead to extension of researches on the use of microorganisms in order to develop application of phytoextraction and to make this method more economical^{5,6}. The adequate restoration of the environment requires co-operation, integration and assimilation of biotechnological approaches along with traditional and ethical wisdom

to conserve our natural resources⁷.

The use of rhizospheric microbes such as arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi (AMF) in phyto/bioremediation of heavy metal contaminated soils has attracted more attention recently. AMF provide direct links between soil and roots and consequently may have an essential contribution to plant growth by improving mineral nutrition and enhancing plant tolerance to stress^{8,9}. Furthermore, AMF also affect metal uptake by plants from soil and translocation from root to shoot, however, mycorrhizal effects may depend on elements, plant and fungal species/ecotypes¹⁰. Arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi *Glomus mosseae* and *Glomus intraradices* are effective in accumulation heavy metals in the root system and its phytotoxic effects, contributing to the phytoremediation of contaminated soils^{11,12}.

Chrysanthemum indicum L. is an abundant ornamental bioresource in India and other parts of the world. It grows in polluted areas surrounding cities. Moreover, the plant possesses key traits that make it very attractive to use in the clean-up of metal-polluted sites, e.g. ease of cultivation, rapid growth, abundant flowering, and a short

life cycle^{13,14}. Such plants require plenty of nutrients such as NO₃, PO₄, Ca, K, Mg, S and micronutrients as well, which can be applied through vermicomposting having ameliorative effects on plant growth and yield as compared to inorganic fertilizers applied to soil¹⁵, which acts as natural fertilizer for phytoremediation studies of heavy metals¹⁶. It contains a high proportion of humic substances (i.e. humic acids, fulvic acids and humin) which provide numerous sites for chemical reaction. Hence, an understanding of the participation of earthworms along with application of elemental S in slightly alkaline soil reaction (pH 7.8 ± 0.2) is basic for enhanced phytoremediation in metal polluted soils.

With the aforesaid perspectives regarding problems associated with cadmium and lead contamination and its possible remediation through integrated micro-biochemical approach for the clean-up of the contaminated soil, the present study was implemented with an aim to explore the possibility of cleaning-up the Cd and Pb-contaminated soils through growing a non-field crop (ornamental plant), *Chrysanthemum indicum* L. during the year 2011–2014 at Sheila Dhar Institute Experimental Farm, Allahabad, India. The objectives of the present study were (1) to compare the biomass production and accumulation cadmium and lead under different treatment combinations with application of vermicompost (VC), S, *Glomus fasciculatum* (AMF), and (2) to investigate the potential of *Chrysanthemum indicum* L. for enhanced cadmium and lead-phytoremediation through application of vermicompost and S and inoculation with arbuscular

mycorrhizal fungi (AMF).

Results and discussion

Effect on dry biomass :

The data presented in Table 1 indicated that combined application of vermicompost, S and AMF (T₆) produced maximum increase in root and shoot dry biomass up to the extent of 21.15% and 33.95%, respectively over the control at the uncontaminated site S₁. The individual application of AMF under sites S₁ and S₂ increased root dry biomass by 15.38% and 20.83% and shoot dry biomass by 26.85% and 28.53%, respectively as compared to control pots^{9,12,17,18}.

The individual application of vermicompost under sites S₁ and S₂ increased root dry biomass by 14.42% and 18.75% and shoot dry biomass by 27.78% and 30.13%, respectively as compared to control pots, which showed ameliorative role of vermicompost on the dry biomass of the plant^{13,19}. Application of S under sites S₁ and S₂ increased root dry biomass by 9.62% and 13.54% and shoot dry biomass by 21.91% and 24.36%, respectively as compared to control pots which indicated ameliorative role of sulphur addition in pots^{20,21}. The comparative study of various treatments revealed the synergistic effect of the integrated micro-biochemical approach towards enhanced phytoremediation. It is expected that the longer the plants stay absorbing metals, the higher will be the amount of metal extracted. Thus high biomass production by plants treated with vermicompost, S and AMF could be a key factor for the removal of cadmium and

Table 1. Effect of vermicompost, elemental sulphur and *Glomus fasciculatum* on dry biomass of *Chrysanthemum indicum* L.

Treatment	Dry biomass (g pot ⁻¹) <i>Chrysanthemum indicum</i> L.			
	S ₁ = Sheila Dhar Institute uncontaminated soil		S ₂ = Naini contaminated soil	
	Root	Shoot	Root	Shoot
T ₀ = Control	1.04 ± 0.05	3.24 ± 0.11	0.96 ± 0.04	3.12 ± 0.05
T ₁ = 6 g kg ⁻¹ vermicompost	1.19 ± 0.07	4.14 ± 0.22	1.14 ± 0.12	4.06 ± 0.23
T ₂ = 0.8 g kg ⁻¹ elemental sulphur	1.14 ± 0.04	3.95 ± 0.19	1.09 ± 0.07	3.88 ± 0.14
T ₃ = Inoculation with AMF	1.20 ± 0.08	4.11 ± 0.23	1.16 ± 0.14	4.01 ± 0.12
T ₄ = 6 g kg ⁻¹ vermicompost + Inoculation with AMF	1.22 ± 0.12	4.24 ± 0.09	1.18 ± 0.13	4.20 ± 0.21
T ₅ = 6 g kg ⁻¹ vermicompost + 0.8 g kg ⁻¹ elemental sulphur	1.21 ± 0.10	4.22 ± 0.20	1.17 ± 0.15	4.18 ± 0.22
T ₆ = 6 g kg ⁻¹ vermicompost + 0.8 g kg ⁻¹ elemental sulphur + Inoculation with AMF	1.26 ± 0.09	4.34 ± 0.22	1.23 ± 0.12	4.28 ± 0.16

Note : ± Values indicate standard error having three replications; AMF = arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi (*Glomus fasciculatum*).

lead from soils.

Effect on accumulation of cadmium and lead in Chrysanthemum indicum L. :

The data graphically presented in Figs. 1(a-b) indicated that different sites S₁ and S₂ were observed significantly ($P < 0.0001$) different in the concentration of Cd and Pb in the root and shoot of *Chrysanthemum indicum* L. Cadmium concentration (in mg kg⁻¹) ranged from 0.17 to 6.69 and 0.15 to 5.66, while Pb concentration (in mg kg⁻¹) ranged from 2.80 to 16.70 and 1.85 to 13.74 in root and shoot, respectively. The effects of vermicompost, S and inoculation with AMF and their integrated application were observed highly significant.

The statistical analysis showed that F-value for column factor (treatments) was observed highly significant for Cd-accumulation in root and shoot (69.37****, $P < 0.0001$).

Similarly F-value for row factor (sites) was observed highly significant for Cd-accumulation in root and shoot (3966****, $P < 0.0001$). The interaction between treatments and sites for Cd-accumulation was also observed highly significant in root and shoot (20.67****, $P < 0.0001$). For Pb-accumulation, F-value for column factor (treatments) was observed highly significant in root and shoot (327.0****, $P < 0.0001$). Similarly F-value for row factor (sites) was observed highly significant for Pb-accumulation in root and shoot (3756****, $P < 0.0001$). The interaction between treatments and sites for Pb-accumulation was also observed highly significant in root and shoot (16.70****, $P < 0.0001$). The integrated treatment T₆ (comprising of vermicompost 6 mg kg⁻¹ + S 0.8 g kg⁻¹ + inoculation with AMF) registered maximum accumulation of Cd up to 6.69 and 5.66 mg kg⁻¹ and Pb up to 16.70 and 13.74

Fig. 1a. Accumulation of cadmium in roots and shoots of *Chrysanthemum indicum* L.

mg kg⁻¹ in root and shoot, respectively, in *Chrysanthemum indicum* L. at site S₂. Almost similar results were reported by Mani *et al.*^{13,18,22}.

The individual inoculation of AMF (*Glomus fasciculatum*) increased Cd and Pb accumulation in root by 78.68% and 48.50%, in shoot by 53.50% and 30.84%, respectively at S₂ site, as compared to control pots. The combined application of 6 g kg⁻¹ vermicompost and inoculation with *Glomus fasciculatum* increased Cd accumulation by 88.89% and 71.02% and Pb accumulation by 87.61% and 55.90% in root and shoot, respectively over the control at site S₂²².

The individual application of vermicompost increased Cd and Pb accumulation in root by 58.56% and 38.27%, in shoot by 36.94% and 25.49%, respectively at S₂ site, as compared to control pots¹³. The combined application of 6 g kg⁻¹ vermicompost and 0.8 g kg⁻¹ S increased Cd accumulation by 84.98% and 57.64% and Pb accumulation by 78.82% and 52.83% in root and shoot, respectively over the control at site S₂. The individual application of S at 0.8 g kg⁻¹ increased Cd and Pb accumulation

in root by 72.67% and 42.72%, in shoot by 43.95% and 28.01%, respectively as compared to control pots at site S₂²³. Elemental S application increased the Cd and Pb solubilization in soil and increased their uptake by plants. The study indicated that S could promote the transformation of cadmium and lead from easily bioavailable fractions to potential bioavailable fractions^{13,20,21}.

The strength of metal-sulphur complexes is highly pH-dependent and most of the stimulatory effects of S on metal availability have been observed in alkaline soils^{20,22}. Thus, vermicompost, S and AMF (*Glomus fasciculatum*) treatments exerted stimulatory effect on plant Cd and Pb availability and found suitable for enhanced phytoremediation potential of *Chrysanthemum indicum* L. through soil plant rhizospheric processes.

Effect on remediation efficiency and bioaccumulation factor :

Addition of vermicompost, S and AMF (*Glomus fasciculatum*) boosted the remediation ratio (RR) and bioaccumulation factor (BF) of cadmium and lead in

Fig. 1b. Accumulation of lead in roots and shoots of *Chrysanthemum indicum* L.

Chrysanthemum indicum L. (Figs. 2(a-b)).

The integrated treatment T₆ registered the maximum RR (0.55%) and BF (2.57) for cadmium at site S₂. It was observed 0.18% and 0.84 for lead. The study revealed that cadmium and lead-contaminated soil clean-up might be achieved through growing *Chrysanthemum indicum* L. and its remediation potential could be enhanced through the integrated application of vermicompost, S, and AMF in the rhizosphere of plants. The strategy for enhanced clean-up of Cd and Pb contaminated soils must be implemented in and around Cd and Pb-contaminated soils, especially along the sewage irrigated, waste water irrigated and Cd and Pb mining areas^{24,25}.

Fuksova *et al.*²⁶ observed lower BFs for Cd in *Salix* (1.01) and *Salix* plus (0.492) at a highly contaminated soil and higher BFs in *Thlaspi* (49.7), *Thlaspi* plus (43.5), *Salix* (7.53) and *Salix* plus (6.28) at a moderately contaminated soil, as compared to the observed BF in *Chrysanthemum indicum* L. (2.57) for Cd under the integrated

treatment at the contaminated site S₂ in the present study. Similarly they reported lower RRs for Cd in *Salix* (0.015) and *Salix* plus (0.032) at the highly contaminated soil and higher RRs in *Thlaspi* (7.55), *Thlaspi* plus (5.02), *Salix* (8.10) and *Salix* plus (3.36) at the moderately contaminated soil as compared to the present findings with *Chrysanthemum indicum* L. (RRs 0.55). Sun *et al.*²⁷ reported lower RR (0.3) for Cd using a hyperaccumulator plant, *Rorippa globosa*, under EDTA treated pots at 0.5 g/kg than that of the integrated treatment at the contaminated site S₂ under the present study. The present study is an integration of chemical (S), phytotechnological (*Chrysanthemum indicum* L.), biotechnological (vermicompost) and microbiological (*Glomus fasciculatum*) approaches for phyto/bioremediation of moderately Cd and Pb-contaminated soils.

Material and methods :

Plant material and experimental layout :

The experimental sites are located between latitudes

Fig. 2a. Effect of different treatments on remediation ratio for Cd and Pb in *Chrysanthemum indicum* L.

Fig. 2b. Effect of different treatments on bioaccumulation factor for Cd and Pb in *Chrysanthemum indicum* L.

25°20'–20°57' N and longitudes 81°52'–81°86' E and belong to the Indian tropical sub-humid region of Indo-Gangetic plain, Allahabad, Uttar Pradesh, India. The soils of Gangetic plain are Alluvial Entisols having some recent origin. The mean texture of the experimental soil was silty clay loam (sand $49.06 \pm 5.65\%$, silt $28.36 \pm 6.53\%$ and clay $22.45 \pm 4.39\%$). The details of site-wise physico-chemical properties are given in Table 2a. Two sites namely Sheila Dhar Institute Farm uncontaminated soil (S₁) and Naini contaminated soil (S₂) are located in the agricultural farms receiving sewage-irrigation for more than 25 years spread around 36 km² of the urban and sub-urban area of Allahabad.

The soil was ground to pass through a 2 mm sieve. Soil was sterilized by steam (at 121 °C) and used as a cultivation bed. Plastic pots of a 2 liter capacity (each containing 2 kg of air dried soil) were used. Seeds were densely sown 1 cm deep but after emergence seedling were thinned to one plant per pot. The experiment was carried out in a natural light condition having daily temperature 28 °C and photoperiod 12.5 h. The experiment

Table 2a. Physico-chemical properties of experimental soils used under the investigation

Parameters	S ₁	S ₂
pH	7.8 ± 0.2	7.6 ± 0.1
EC (dSm ⁻¹) at 25 °C	0.28 ± 0.03	1.24 ± 0.03
Organic carbon (g kg ⁻¹)	3.45 ± 0.15	4.76 ± 0.15
CEC [C mol (p ⁺) kg ⁻¹]	19.6 ± 0.64	22.1 ± 1.64
Total N (%)	0.07 ± 0.01	0.08 ± 0.01
Total P ₂ O ₅ (%)	0.036 ± 0.004	0.038 ± 0.006
Total Cd (mg kg ⁻¹)	0.12 ± 0.01	2.2 ± 0.10
Total Pb (mg kg ⁻¹)	9.60 ± 2.7	16.4 ± 1.24
Sand (%)	54.48 ± 2.46	49.5 ± 3.25
Silt (%)	20.86 ± 1.25	32.8 ± 2.45
Clay (%)	24.65 ± 2.76	17.4 ± 1.75

Note : ± Values indicate standard error having three replications, N = Nitrogen, P₂O₅ = Phosphorus, EC = Electrical conductivity, CEC = Cation exchange capacity, Cd = Cadmium, Pb = Lead; S₁ = Sheila Dhar Institute uncontaminated soil, S₂ = Naini contaminated soil.

was replicated thrice and conducted in completely randomized block design following seven treatments. Total 42 plastic pots [having 7 treatments replicated thrice and

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two sites (S_1 and S_2) were installed. The treatment combinations have been mentioned under Table 1.

All the chemicals used in the study were of analytical reagent (AR) grade. Sulphur was applied as elemental sulphur. In order to allow the stabilization of adsorption-desorption reactions, soils were incubated with VC for one month at field water capacity (80%) before planting *Chrysanthemum*. Elemental sulphur was applied in the pots before the transplantation of the seedlings. The quality of VC is given under Table 2b. Soil moisture was maintained by irrigating the crops at interval of 2–3 days. *Chrysanthemum indicum* L. was grown as a test crop and harvested at 60 days after transplanting for the aforesaid analysis. The plant samples were oven-dried at 60 °C for biochemical analysis and at 70–80 °C for the analysis of cadmium and lead.

Table 2b. Physico-chemical properties of applied vermicompost used under the investigation

Parameters	Vermicompost
pH	6.8 ± 0.2
EC (dS/m) at 25 °C	1.06 ± 0.08
Organic carbon (%)	13.50 ± 0.38
CEC [C mol (p ⁺)/kg]	86 ± 9.6
Total nitrogen (%)	1.33 ± 0.22
Total phosphorus (%)	0.47 ± 0.29
Total Pb (mg kg ⁻¹)	0.16 ± 0.03
DTPA-extractable Pb (mg kg ⁻¹)	0.07 ± 0.02

Note : ± Values indicate standard error having three replications; EC = Electrical conductivity, CEC = Cation exchange capacity, DTPA = Di-ethyl tri-amine penta acetic acid.

Soil sampling and extraction of heavy metals from soil :

In each sampling unit, soil samples were drawn from several spots in a zigzag pattern, leaving about 2 m area along the field margins. Silt and clay were separated by Pipette method and fine sand by decantation method. For total Cd and Pb content, one gram of soil was mixed in 5 ml of HNO₃ (16 M, 71%) and 5 ml of HClO₄ (11 M, 71%). The composite was heated up to dryness. The volume was made up to 50 ml with hot distilled water. The clean filtrate was used for the estimation of heavy metals using Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometer (AAS) (AAnalyst600, Perkin-Elmer Inc., MA, USA)²⁸.

Soil physico-chemical analysis :

Soil pH was measured with 1 : 2.5 soil water ratio using Elico digital pH meter (Model LI 127, Elico Ltd., Hyderabad, India) at authors' laboratory. Double distilled water was used for the preparation of all solutions. Organic carbon was determined by chromic acid digestion method, cation exchange capacity (CEC) by neutral 1 N ammonium acetate solution, total nitrogen by digestion mixture (containing sulphuric acid, selenium dioxide and salicylic acid) using micro-Kjeldahl method, Glass Agencies, Ambala, India. Total phosphorus by hot plate digestion with HNO₃ (16 M, 71%) and extraction by standard ammonium molybdate solution²⁹.

Microbial culture and inoculation method :

Arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi [*Glomus fasciculatum* (isolate GF1)] were purchased from microbial culture collection of CSIR-CIMAP, Bangalore, India. *Glomus fasciculatum* was maintained as a pot culture using sterilized sand : soil mixture (1 : 1 by volume) as the substrate and onion plants were used as the host was used in the experiments. After 75 days of growth, roots of onion plant were severed and the pot ball consisting of the root system plus substrate was finely chopped and air dried to constitute the mycorrhizal inoculum. Twenty-five g of this inoculum containing approximately 150 spores/g was used for inoculation of each pot.

Plant analysis :

Plants were harvested after 60 days having higher phytochemicals at their maturity stage as suggested by Mani *et al.*³⁰. Samples were carefully rinsed with tap water followed by 0.2% detergent solution, 0.1 N HCl, de-ionized water, and double distilled water.

Samples were dried in a hot-air oven at a temperature of 60 °C, and ground to a fine powder. Plant dry biomass weight was recorded. One gram of ground plant material was digested with 15 ml of tri-acid mixture (Kumar and Mani²⁸) containing conc. HNO₃ (16 M, 71%), H₂SO₄ (18 M, 96%) and HClO₄ (11 M, 71%) in 5 : 1 : 2), heated on hot plate at low heat (60 °C) for 30 min and total heavy metals were determined by the aforesaid spectrophotometer.

Bioaccumulation factor and remediation ratio :

Bioaccumulation factor (BF) is calculated according

to the following formula.

$$BF = \frac{M_{\text{shoot}}}{M_{\text{soil}}}$$

where, M_{shoot} is the metal content (mg/kg dry wt) in shoots, M_{soil} is the total metal content (mg/kg) in the soil.

Remediation ratio (RR) :

The remediation ratio (RR) is defined as the ratio of an element accumulation in shoot to that in soil, which is calculated as follows :

$$RR = \frac{M_{\text{shoot}} \times W_{\text{shoot}}}{M_{\text{soil}} \times W_{\text{soil}}} \times 100$$

where M_{shoot} is the metal concentration in shoots of the plants (mg/kg), W_{shoot} is the plant dry above ground biomass (g), M_{soil} is the metal content in soil (mg/kg) and W_{soil} is the weight of soil in the pot (g). The RR values reflect the amount of a metal remediation by a plant from soil (Sun *et al.*²⁷).

Statistical analysis :

Data were analyzed by factorial analysis of variation (ANOVA) using various treatments as independent factors with the help of the sum of square (SS) and degree of freedom (DF). The standard error (SE) is given by $SE =$

$\sqrt{\frac{2V_E}{n}}$, where V_E is the variance due to the error, n is the number of replications. All treatments were replicated thrice in the experiment. Graph Pad Prism (version 6, Graph Pad Software, USA) software was used for drawing figures.

Conclusion

Inoculation with AM fungi showed synergistic effect, rather than their individual effects, on the dry biomass and phytoremediation potential of the tested plant *Chrysanthemum indicum* L. Maximum bioaccumulation factor for cadmium (2.57) and lead (0.84) was observed in the targeted treatment T₆ comprising of an integrated approach of applying vermicompost, S, and arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi. The integrated approach showed maximum remediation ratio of cadmium (0.55%) and lead (0.18%) at the contaminated site S₂ indicating enhanced

phytoremediation of cadmium and lead through *Chrysanthemum indicum* L. in the cadmium and lead contaminated soil.

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